

Psychosocial risk in customer service staff: Reduction strategies in the financial sector

Riesgo psicosocial en personal de atención al cliente: Estrategias de reducción en el sector financiero

Risco psicossocial em equipe de atendimento: Estratégias de redução no setor financeiro

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ABSTRACT

Currently, psychosocial risk is spoken of as one of the most important factors in companies today, since these are the ones that affect the mental health of workers and their productivity in their work. Strategies have been carried out for many years worldwide to be able to address prevention and help reduce the risk and its impact on people. A review was made of the most recent research on the significance of psychosocial risk in customer service personnel and reduction strategies in the financial sector. The main objective of this review article is to qualitatively analyze the scientific literature available in the databases Science Direct, Scielo, Redalyc, Google academic and official websites, using as search words: psychosocial risk, customer service, companies, sector financial, stress. Pertinent information related to the proposed objective was obtained, which is presented in 3 sections: psychosocial risk, causes and consequences; customer service personnel, task characteristics and psychosocial risk reduction strategies in the financial sector. Psychosocial risks can be generated from any factor, whether internal or external, from different areas, understanding the human being as a multidimensional being, which is why the best strategy to reduce them is to work from prevention, generating clear procedures, programs, training for area leaders and creating an organizational culture.

Keywords: Customer service, Work stress, Psychosocial risk, Financial sector.

RESUMEN

En la actualidad se habla de riesgo psicosocial como uno de los factores más importantes hoy en las empresas, ya que son estos los que afectan la salud mental de los trabajadores y la productividad de estos en sus labores, se han realizado desde hace muchos años estrategias a nivel mundial para poder abordar desde la prevención y ayudar a la disminución del riesgo y

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la afectación de este en las personas. Se hizo una revisión sobre las investigaciones más recientes acerca de la trascendencia del riesgo psicosocial en el personal de atención al cliente y las estrategias de reducción en el sector financiero. El presente artículo de revisión tiene como principal objetivo analizar cualitativamente la literatura científica disponible en las bases de datos Science Direct, Scielo, Redalyc, Google académico y páginas Web oficiales, empleando como palabras de búsqueda: riesgo psicosocial, atención al cliente, empresas, sector financiero, estrés. Se obtuvo información pertinente relacionada con el objetivo propuesto, la cual se presenta en 3 secciones: riesgo psicosocial, causas y consecuencias; personal de atención al cliente, características de la tarea y estrategias de reducción del riesgo psicosocial en el sector financiero. Los riesgos psicosociales pueden generarse a partir de cualquier factor ya sea interno o externo, desde diferentes ámbitos, entendiendo al ser humano como un ser multidimensional, es por esto que la mejor estrategia para reducirlos es trabajar desde la prevención, generando procedimientos claros, programas, capacitaciones a los líderes de áreas y creando una cultura organizacional.

Palabras clave: Atención al cliente, Estrés laboral, Riesgo psicosocial, Sector financiero.

RESUMO

Atualmente, fala-se do risco psicossocial como um dos fatores mais importantes nas empresas, uma vez que são estes que afetam a saúde mental dos trabalhadores e a sua produtividade no trabalho. Para abordar a prevenção e ajudar a reduzir o risco e o seu impacto nas pessoas. Foi feita uma revisão das pesquisas mais recentes sobre a importância do risco psicossocial no pessoal de atendimento ao cliente e estratégias de redução no setor financeiro. O objetivo principal deste artigo de revisão é analisar qualitativamente a produção científica disponível nas bases de dados Science Direct, Scielo, Redalyc, Google académico e sites oficiais, utilizando como palavras de busca: risco psicossocial, atendimento ao cliente, empresas, setor financeiro, estresse. Foram obtidas informações pertinentes relacionadas ao objetivo proposto, as quais são apresentadas em 3 seções: risco psicossocial, causas e consequências; pessoal de atendimento ao cliente, características das tarefas e estratégias de redução de riscos psicossociais no setor financeiro. Os riscos psicossociais podem ser gerados a partir de qualquer fator, seja interno ou externo, de diversas áreas, entendendo o ser humano como um ser multidimensional, por isso a melhor estratégia para reduzi-los é trabalhar a partir da prevenção, gerando procedimentos, programas, área de formação claros líderes e criando uma cultura organizacional.

Palavras-chave: Atendimento ao cliente, Estresse laboral, Risco psicossocial, Setor financeiro.

INTRODUCTION

Human health and mental health is an aspect that requires sufficient attention today, because the constant changes in which people are immersed can generate negative consequences for each person and can endanger well-being, which is why Psychosocial risks are conditions that are present in the people intra-work (stress, workplace harassment, conflicts with colleagues, overload) and extra-work (family, economic conflicts, etc.)

(Fernández, 2023; García et al., 2020). The sum of all these factors is what puts people's mental health at risk (Fajardo, 2023; Rojas et al., 2022; Puerto et al., 2017).

These risks have become an important factor for companies in recent years. Their appearance is largely related to objective conditions inherent to work and they usually manifest themselves through reactions such as stress in employees. This has come to generate a great impact on the quality of life of people, their families and environment, and are increasingly becoming more relevant, since it becomes a sustained increase in work disability (Arenas et al., 2023, Vásquez et al., 2019; Gómez et al., 2017).

The financial sector, its customer service areas, is greatly affected since its employees suffer from manifestations such as tachycardia, high blood pressure, sweating, respiratory rhythm alterations, pupil dilation, and skin diseases as a result of the execution of their tasks. and hair loss, all of these are pathologies that these people face due to their work stress.(Garzón de Espinosa, 2022;Alarcón, 2018). Today there are promotion and prevention programs that are carried out to mitigate psychosocial risk factors, however, they do not participate in the activities because they do not have the time since their positions generally depend on the goals met (Rangel et al. ..., 2023; García et al., 2020).

In this bibliographic review, a comprehensive review has been made of psychosocial risks, their causes and consequences, how they affect the work of people in different sectors, emphasizing customer service and, most importantly, what are the strategies that companies can implement to reduce it.

PSYCHOSOCIAL RISKS: CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES

Psychosocial risks can be generated from any external factor to which the subject is exposed, which meets the criteria to produce a psychosocial consequence. The psychosocial consequences are many, however, among the most common we have anxieties, stress, attachment, psychosomatic disorders, emotional exhaustion (Camacho & Mayorga, 2017; Moreno & Baez, 2011).

In the same sense, Martínez et al. (2023), points out that anxiety is a warning signal, which will warn the individual of an upcoming danger and allows the subject to adopt measures and strategies to face that threat, therefore, anxiety is a normal response, of the being. human in which adaptability is sought in the face of any danger that affects one's integrity and well-being. Anxiety alerts the individual to execute the necessary actions to avoid dangers through the subsystems of the Nervous System (SN), these being the Sympathetic and Parasympathetic Nervous System.

In turn, Pelissolo (2012) highlights that when anxiety becomes pathological it can cease to be a normal reaction and become a pathology in two different contexts; The first of these scenarios is when the symptoms planned in the DMS-V occur and the second is in which the diagnosis of a chronic anxiety disorder has already been made, such as phobias, panic disorder, or obsessive-compulsive disorders (OCD). When you already have a clear diagnosis, the treatment stage of the disorder begins where the most effective techniques are those proposed by the cognitive behavioral approach and sometimes antidepressants.

On the other hand, there are Acute Stress Disorder (ASD) and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), which according to Crespo et al. (2019), arise as a result of experiencing a trauma or traumatic event that is perceived by the individual as a significant threat in the physical, emotional or psychological sphere, either directly or to an individual with whom he or she has some type of relationship. They also mention in this research that of the world population that is exposed to a traumatic event, around 25 – 30% of people develop ASD and PTSD. This is why the prevalence of these disorders is part of the focus of this research, since, for their generation, it is necessary that individual, but also environmental, vulnerability factors are present.

In accordance with the above, to adopt any of these disorders, it is necessary that individual, environmental and emotional factors be present that influence their development. In addition to this, there are some criteria that must be met exactly to achieve the final diagnosis. Among the socio-emotional or environmental factors are romantic relationships with the partner, where depending on the course of the relationship, it may or may not be violent. According to Argüello & Costales (2022), victims of intimate partner violence, in this case, women, have a greater tendency to develop anxiety disorders, depression and PTSD, due to how exposed they are to the socio-environmental and emotional factor of violence. as a couple

Additionally, there are emotional predisposing factors where antecedents can be found such as situations of abandonment, pending unresolved issues, lack of emotional tools to face difficult situations, terminal or degenerative illnesses, which more easily generate anxiety, stress and depression. Each individual reacts differently to these emotional factors, some assimilate them as opportunities to improve themselves, but other people increase anxiety levels. It is worth noting what López (2007) mentions, sometimes sadness is confused with depression and depression with a psychiatric diagnosis; however, a symptom like sadness does not have to be pathological, it is just a symptom of the depressive disorder. of personality, and even simpler it can be just a symptom of depressive syndrome.

In the words of Muñoz et al. (2018), the factors that cause psychosocial risk are varied: workload, economic pressures (household debt), lack of recognition for the work done, demand or need. of working overtime, the impossibility of meeting the operational demands of the job and unattainable personal or work expectations, among others. The above causes the worker to inevitably suffer the consequences of psychosocial risk, affecting not only individuality but also the environment.

The main consequence of psychosocial risk is stress, whose most frequent symptoms range from irritability to depression and are generally accompanied by physical and mental exhaustion. In this way, stress directly affects the worker's performance, causing low productivity and affecting work comfort. And the fact is that a person subjected to very high tension is incapable of making correct decisions and his creativity significantly decreases, since the mind is incapable of finding the multiple solutions that are required for successful performance. Güilgüiruca et al., (2015) They state in this regard that a company with many stressed people generally has a bad work environment.

Psychosocial risk is part of a group of occupational risks which are situations that can put the physical and psychological well-being of a company's workers at risk, thus affecting their work capacity, performance, productivity, among others. This concept over the years has evolved in accordance with the development of industries and different economic sectors; there have been government institutions interested in the regulation of this issue, which has caused greater attention and documentation (Jiménez, 2011).

Knowing the consequences for the employer, it is important to know the consequences for the employee, who is a fundamental part of the development of the company's economic activity. The employee as a human resource must be under favorable intra-work and extra-work conditions to perform their duties with the expected results. However, this is not always the case, on some occasions the employee is exposed to risk directly or indirectly, generating negative psychological, physical and social behaviors, mental disorders such as stress, or burnout, generalized anxiety, panic disorder, depression, even physical conditions, through somatization, such as gastritis, headaches, intestinal disorders, high blood pressure, among others (Gil-Monte, 2009).

Psychosocial risks are increasingly present in everyday life, and day by day people are becoming aware of this fact, which is how different authors and researchers emerge who address this topic. But despite everything we are seeing, this is not enough because more factors continue to appear and this means that in recent years the rate of psychosocial risks at work has increased.

To understand this phenomenon, one must begin by knowing what factors affect psychosocial risk and for this, different studies have been found, such as the one published by the ILO in 1984 “Psychosocial factors at work: Recognition and Control”, in which It is known what the psychosocial factors are at work and what consequences they have for the health of employees.

Then there is another document where the starting point is found, it is recognized that psychosocial risks influence health and it is with the study published by the WHO in 1988 “Psychosocial factors at work and their relationship with health” this work It is intended for “Managers as well as health personnel and has the purpose of enabling them to create appropriate occupational hygiene services, develop methods for monitoring and evaluating the psychosocial work environment and the health of workers exposed to it, and determine the need for new research” (Kalimo et al., 2000).

There are various factors or causes from which psychosocial risks derive; therefore, Table 1 shows the different investigations that mention the possible causes, which makes it easier to have a simpler and broader view of the reasons why. psychosocial risks occur at work.

Table 1. Some studies associated with psychosocial risk

Country	Qualification	Author / Year
Spain	Some reasons to consider psychosocial risks at work and their consequences.	Gil-Monte (2009)

Spain	Psychosocial occupational factors and risks.	Moreno (2011)
Mexico	Occupational Burnout Syndrome and its Relationship with Health and Psychosocial Risk in Public Officials Imparting Justice in Mexico City	Uribe & López (2014)
Colombia	Intra-workplace psychosocial factors in professionals with staff in charge in the city of Bucaramanga.	Rodríguez (2014)
Spain	Psychosocial risks: causes, consequences and possible solutions	Espeleta (2015)
Uruguay	Burnout and Psychosocial Risk Factors in Call Centers.	Tortora (2016)
Argentina	Psychosocial risk factors in work contexts of agricultural extension workers in Argentina.	Cacivio (2017)
Spain	Primary care approach to psychosocial risks in the work environment.	Sequeiro (2019)
Spain	Influence of the acculturation process on the perception of psychosocial risks at work.	Moreno (2020)
Ecuador	Psychosocial Risk and job performance.	Guaman (2021)
Colombia	Analysis of Causes, Effects and Consequences of Psychosocial Risk.	Serrano & Vargas (2022)
Ecuador	Consequences of psychosocial risks on the performance of workers at a Port terminal in Guayaquil.	Encalada (2022)

Source: Self made

From the above, it is outlined that psychosocial risks can favor or harm people's work activity and quality of work life since they promote the personal development of individuals, while when they are unfavorable they harm their health and well-being, it is for This must be worked on from preventive medicine since this is a combination of medical practices designed to avoid common and occupational diseases. The occupational health and safety system is a system designed for the prevention of risks in companies and for this all possible causes that affect the system are analyzed.

This is why all companies must analyze their problems and thus be able to combat them, according to Perdomo (2014) ensures that improving the health of workers is directly related to how productive and profitable organizations can become, for this reason to implement a good SGSST we must know the company in its entirety, see the importance of the

occupational health of companies, and not only react when an unfortunate event occurs with an employee or when lawsuits must be faced for non-compliance with labor standards.

There is much research worldwide, for example in China Wang et al. (2023) initiated an investigation of How work stress and psychological adaptation predict interpersonal needs among migrant manufacturing workers, in which workers from 16 manufacturing factories participated. , being a total sample of 507 people where it was found that work stress was directly associated with mood states and interpersonal needs, psychological adaptation was directly associated with mood states and indirectly with interpersonal needs.

At the Latin American level, in Chile, Gülgüiruca et al. (2015) state in their research on the psychosocial risk factors and perceived stress in workers of a company in the electricity sector that, the workers state that to the extent The risk perception of psychosocial factors at work increases, their stress levels also increase, thus highlighting that all factors such as the relationship between gender, double presence, social and work support, active work, shift system and compensation, have as a consequence the impact on stress levels, although they are not directly related to the worker, it is enough for the presence of the psychosocial risk factor to be perceived.

In Colombia, there is a list of diseases, which is divided by risks, in terms of psychosocial risk, we have acute and transient Psychotic Disorders, Depression, Panic Disorder, Anxiety Disorders, Adaptation Disorders, Adaptive Disorders with Anxious Mood, with Depressed mood, with Mixed mood, with Behavioral Alterations or Mixed with Emotional and Behavioral Alterations, Arterial Hypertension, Ischemic Heart Disease, Acute Myocardial Infarction, Cerebrovascular Diseases, Encephalopathy, Ulcers, Chronic Gastritis, Dyspepsia, Irritable Bowel Syndrome , Sleep Disorder, Post-Traumatic Stress. All these diseases are described and coded in the ICD-10. (Ministry of Labor, 2014)

Based on the recognition of psychosocial risks, in Colombia more and more cases have been identified in which workers in all economic sectors develop related pathologies, thus prompting the regulatory body, in this case the Ministry of Labor, to generate intervention proposals. In order to manage the action of psychosocial risks in the worker, for example, the “Es 3 Bajo 0” program has been developed aimed at expanding the understanding of the concept of stress and its functionality as a process of adaptation to the work environment (Lizcano 2018).

CUSTOMER SERVICE STAFF: TASK CHARACTERISTICS

Customer service is defined for all types of companies, whether public, private or mixed, whether large, medium or small, with activities of any type of industrial, manufacturing or service, all of these people intervene or are involved in the customer service due to the existence of not only external, but also internal clients, each area communicates with another, thus waiting for attention. This is why customer service is not a decision but an important element in the development of the company.

But we must begin by understanding what service is and there are multiple definitions, but all always with the same sense of relationship. For example, Peel (1993) says that service

is the activity that relates the company to the customer, so that he is satisfied with said activity, on the other hand Gaither (1983) says that customer service is a range of activities that together create a relationship, a slightly broader definition than that presented by Lovelock (1990) who says that customer service involves task-oriented activities, other than proactive selling, that include interactions with customers in person, via telecommunications, or by mail. This function must be designed, performed and communicated with two objectives in mind: customer satisfaction and operational efficiency.

These definitions allow us to understand the importance of service in any type of activity carried out. Taking a focus on the business world, we find that Couso, RP (2005), says that customer service is “All the activities that link the company with its customers”, within these activities they mention the most relevant ones:

- The activities necessary to ensure that products and services are delivered on time, in units and in presentation to customers.
- The relationships between company and clients.
- After-sales services.
- Complaints, requests and information services to clients.

The world is becoming more globalized every day, seeking development and characterized by constant change and transformation. As part of this globalization and this change, there is a lot of talk about customer service and how organizations work in search of customer satisfaction. Nowadays, the globalization of customer service means that all staff in an organization are capable of providing a response to the customer, being able to guide them to obtain the information or service they are looking for. Good service is having the appropriate response at the moment. appropriate.

When we talk about customer service we must also talk about quality, because they are two things that go hand in hand to achieve satisfaction. It can be understood that a product is quality when the customer receives what they expect, while quality service is how they receive it. Quality is essential, but the warmth of the service is what gives the greatest customer satisfaction. Therefore, in addition to quality, the concept of warmth must be incorporated into the service and ensure that all people in the organization work in it.

Customer service is not only given for organizational issues of companies dedicated to the sale of products or services, a role that has gained a lot of strength in recent years is service through social work. Based on their values and principles, companies are directing efforts towards corporate social responsibility. According to Robbins & Jugde (2017), social responsibility is considered as the voluntary attitude of the company aimed at satisfying the social demands of the different related agents, derived from the effects that business activity causes on them.

The growth in social responsibility programs has generated benefits not only to the internal parts of the companies but also to the communities, Parra, et al., (2019) maintain that organizations are in favor of dedicating efforts to programs aimed at improving their physical-social environment, generating programs and activities for employees, but they also

work on the growth and development of external communities, and this causes an influence positive in people, in order to increase sales and the image of the company.

This is why companies seek to be increasingly competitive, highlighting the customer as the central element of the processes, as well as recognizing the internal employee as a customer and in this search for competitiveness, satisfaction and delivery of value, comes a very important element that helps the development of the service is technology, this has become a fundamental part to properly manage company processes and achieve employee satisfaction.

PSYCHOSOCIAL RISK REDUCTION STRATEGIES IN THE FINANCIAL SECTOR

Psychosocial Risks have been present for many years. Kornhauser (1965) says that since the 1960s, organizational and management practices have influenced the mental health of workers and that their impact varies depending on the organization and the activities it carries out. the employee. However, it is very recent that the world has been concerned about the well-being of workers, making changes in management practices and occupational health and safety.

Psychosocial factors related to work in recent years have been growing throughout the world, as a result of this many studies have been presented on how to confront and prevent them. Currently there are other factors that can affect safety and health at work, such as chemical, biological, physical, ergonomic and mechanical factors, but clear control strategies have not been developed for psychosocial factors. The strategies that have been found in the literature have emerged from the subjective perceptions of different companies (Sáenz & Ugalde, 2019).

According to Luna Chávez et al. (2021), in the report of the Joint Committee International Labor Organization (ILO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) on occupational medicine, psychosocial factors were defined as: Interactions between work, their environment, job satisfaction and the conditions of their organization, on the one hand, and on the other, the worker's capabilities, their needs, their culture and their personal situation outside of work, all of which, Through perceptions and experiences, they can exert a harmful influence on health, performance and satisfaction at work.

The main manifestation of psychosocial risk is stress. Its main effects, such as violence, workplace harassment or sexual harassment, directly affect the person's functioning. According to the research article Muñoz Rojas et al. (2018), after these effects, other forms of psychosocial risks may arise, such as job insecurity or Burnout syndrome or professional burnout, which affect the organization, and can even lead to the somatization of these behaviors, manifesting in diseases that directly affect the productivity of companies.

In this same article, Muñoz Rojas et al. (2018) tells us that it is important to identify the psychosocial and organizational factors that affect productivity and well-being at work, in order to develop appropriate strategies to counteract their negative effects, and generate recovery plans. action that leads us to the satisfaction of the organizational and personal needs

and objectives of employees. The preventive strategy has been consolidated as the first step in promoting well-being at work; organizations have understood that if there is physical, moral and social comfort, the objectives will be achieved more easily.

Companies, before planning and implementing strategies to reduce psychosocial risk factors, must know in detail what are the intra- and extra-occupational factors to which workers are exposed; to this end, in each country there are instruments endorsed for their application to the working population, including the financial sector, which identify the factors taking into account the nature of the economic activity, the activities of the company and the characteristics of the population.

In Chile, for example, there is the SUSESO/ISTAS21 questionnaire, Candia & Pérez (2020), which is a translation made by Spain of the adaptation of the psychosocial risk questionnaire from Copenhagen – Denmark. This questionnaire is also applied in countries such as Argentina, United Kingdom, Belgium, Germany, Brazil, Netherlands, Sweden, among others. The questionnaire has two versions, the short version and the full version, and measures 5 dimensions (each dimension has other subdimensions):

1. Quantitative Psychological Demands
2. Active Work and Skill Development
3. Social Support in the Company and Quality of Leadership
4. Compensations
5. Double Presence

In Mexico they have an information guide NOM-035-STPS-2018 where the procedures for the identification, analysis and prevention of psychosocial risk factors at work are found. This guide describes the general provisions for the application of two questionnaires called “Reference Guide II” which applies to companies with less than 50 workers and “Reference Guide III” which applies to companies with more than 50 workers (secretary of labor and social security, 2018).

On the contrary, in countries like Peru there are few valid tools for measuring psychosocial risk factors; however, as in most countries, they have the duty to measure and evaluate risks, therefore, in the In 2017, a project was started with the purpose of validating the Battery of Psychosocial Risk Factors, which is the instrument validated in Colombia for the evaluation of intra- and extra-work factors of workers (Albarrán et al., 2017).

Ecuador uses a tool called the Psychosocial Risk Questionnaire, which consists of 83 items, through which 8 dimensions are measured: Pooping and Work Pace, Development of Competencies, Leadership, Margin of action and Control, Organization of the Work, Recovery, Support and Support and finally Other important points.

In colombiaThere is a battery of instruments for the evaluation of psychosocial risk factors in companies, determined under Resolution 2764 of 2022, with the application of this we can evaluate the intra-work, extra-work risk and the stress that employees face in a company. company and be able to establish some actions to improve the work environment, well-being and quality of work life.

It is important to know the data that Colombia currently presents in order to find those strategies that will serve to control, minimize or mitigate these psychosocial risk factors of the working population. During recent years, mental pathologies derived from stress have increased by up to 43%. Two out of three workers report being exposed to psychosocial risk factors and between 20% and 33% report feeling high levels of stress (Ministry of Labor, 2019).

Some of the physiological consequences suffered by employees of the financial sector in Colombia as a result of carrying out their work tasks are: “tachycardia, high blood pressure, sweating, respiratory rhythm alterations, pupil dilation, skin diseases and hair loss”. On the other hand, there are the consequences at a cognitive level, such as “a feeling of worry, indecision, bad mood, hypersensitivity to criticism and feelings of lack of control”, this being the beginning of a possible mental pathology of work origin (Gómez et al., 2017; Walter, 2015).

Sanabria et al. (2022), maintain in their research carried out on the management of mental health in companies in the financial sector, that the majority of workers in this sector have knowledge of the activities of promotion and prevention programs. that are carried out to mitigate psychosocial risk factors, however, they do not participate in the activities because they do not have the time and they must meet expected monthly results according to their positions, which in most cases, their stability work depends on the goals achieved.

From all the bibliography found, the following table was constructed where the different measures or controls that are exercised on the three generators of psychosocial risk factors are identified, which are the source, the environment and the individual, which make up the scope. intra-labor, such as the non-labor environment of companies in the financial sector. The following results were obtained from the synthesis, see Table 2.

Table 2. Strategies to reduce psychosocial risk factors.

Fountain	Half	Individual
Adopt measures so that internal communication is favorable, so that the worker is informed of the company's times, changes, new structures or activities	Conduct training for the leaders of each process, in leadership styles and how to manage efficient and effective work teams.	Provide training to workers about the risks to which they are exposed, including psychosocial risks, this allows them to have strategies, resources and tools to face the risks that they are immersed in the development of their tasks.
Define company procedures and characterization of tasks to facilitate decision making, design, planning and execution of the objectives of each position	Establish roles with specific tasks for each position and department.	Allow workers to have spaces for participation and collaboration to generate ideas that help with the construction of processes,

		action plans or any activity that is in sync with the achievement of the company's objectives.
Carry out methods and time studies in order to identify indicators grounded in the reality of the company, the workers and their development difficulties.	Plan and execute an Active Break program with the time and frequency required according to each position, where mental health is taken into account.	It generates confidence in the worker, showing how important their opinion and proactivity are in the company.

Source: Self made

In general, it can be seen in the table that the controls that are applied to reduce, despite being few, are the most common and the most effective. The most advisable thing is to take measures that are of a general nature, in order to carry out global approach activities and subsequently start individual activities when the worker is more receptive to the issue, however, the total commitment of senior management and the management of the companies, as well as the approval of the resources necessary for the execution of the evaluation, prevention and control programs of psychosocial risks (Muñoz, et al., 2018).

The most advisable thing is to take measures that are of a general nature, in order to carry out global approach activities and subsequently begin individual activities when the worker is more receptive to the issue and open to prevention and treatment (Valencia et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION

In companies dedicated to customer service, psychosocial risks are almost always generated by work stress and in most companies these factors are not being managed preventively, although different tools have been created at the national and international level. company, taking into account the main reason why the working population in the financial area does not attend the prevention and promotion activities of this risk. This reason is lack of time, since the way in which job stability is guaranteed is the achievement of goals. Companies must carry out management strategies based on prevention to achieve the reduction of these. It is concluded that the best strategy that a company can have to reduce psychosocial risks is to work on them from prevention, generating clear procedures, prevention programs, training for area leaders and providing confidence in workers, showing how important their opinion is. and proactivity in the company, work to modify the organizational climate and culture, incorporating the corresponding concepts of psychosocial risks and their prevention. By raising awareness, measuring and managing psychosocial risks, we will be able to contribute to improving the health, well-being and quality of life of workers.

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